

COLDSPARK® DRIVEN ENERGY AND COST-EFFICIENT METHANE CRACKING FOR HYDROGEN PRODUCTION

D7.8. Report on Carbon Market Potential and Business Opportunities

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DEC	Websites, patent filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
DMP	Data management plan	<input type="checkbox"/>
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The ColdSpark® project will validate a novel non-thermal plasma technology to produce hydrogen at an industrial scale from methane, with a process energy efficiency of 79%, achieving a conversion rate of 85% aiming at zero CO₂ emissions. This will be achieved by designing an industrial-relevant reactor that leverages the best features of the non-thermal plasma technologies, gliding arc and corona discharge, to ensure high efficiency and scalability. The innovation addresses for the first time the critical step of matching the reactor with a pulsed power supply. It enables perfect fine-tuning of the cracking process parameters, to find the right electron density and energy distribution in the plasma reactor, to maximize energy efficiency. The up-and-downstream gas management will be optimised to further contribute to the system’s compatibility with the existing infrastructure. The project will develop and test a novel plasma reactor at lab scale and validate it in conjunction with the power supply at a large scale, pursuing the industry’s most power-efficient generation of hydrogen alongside high-value carbon. The technology will assess its application for both, natural gas and biomethane producers. A low energy cost (< 15 kWh/kg H₂ produced) without the need for catalysts and water, makes the proposed solution the most cost-competitive, environment-friendly, and less complex to implement. The reactor design and modularity bring lower CAPEX and OPEX and make it easily scalable and flexible. The project gathers the expertise of a mix of academic, research, and industrial partners from five countries, which bring both outstanding research and topic competence, as well as knowledge and access to the solution for end-user industries.

ColdSpark® is built on a strong consortium of 7 partners from Norway, Spain, Bulgaria, Germany, and the UK with SEID AS as a Coordinator.

More information about the project can be found at: <http://www.ColdSpark.eu/>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main objective of this report is to provide an overview of the current market potential of elemental carbon and include a literature survey and a few analytical results from carbon produced from the ColdSpark® project.

This report discusses the analysis and characterization of carbon produced by SEID AS, Norway, obtained by cracking pure methane using non-thermal plasma technology. The ColdSpark® reactor optimisation is still going on and it should be noted that the results included in this report may change during further optimization of the plasma reactor and high-voltage power supply.

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
GA	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
EC	European Commission
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
KER	Key Exploitation Result
IEC	Innovation and Exploitation Committee
CB	Carbon Black
TEM	Transmission electron microscope
SEM	Scanning electron microscope
XRD	X-Ray diffraction
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats

PEST	Political, Economic, Social and Technological
ETS	Emissions Trading System
PAH	Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon

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Introduction

Objectives of Carbon Market Analysis

Carbon black (CB) is widely used in several industries to enhance materials' electrical, mechanical and optical properties. CB production is a complex and energy-intensive process to manufacture fine black powder composed of nearly pure elemental carbon. CB has a wide range of industrial applications, primarily as a reinforcing agent in rubber products, and automotive rubber products, paints, plastics, and coatings. CB is manufactured under controlled conditions to produce a variety of CB grades with specific properties such as specific surface area, particle size, structure, conductivity, pore size, abrasion resistance, and colour.

CB has been produced commercially for over 100 years. According to Fortune Business Insights, the global CB market size was priced at USD 27.44 billion in 2023 and is expected to grow from USD 28.76 billion in 2024 to USD 41.28 billion by 2032, demonstrating a compound annual growth rate of 4.6 % during this period (Business Insights, 2024).

CB is produced by several well-established manufacturing processes such as the oil furnace process, the thermal black process, the acetylene black process, the lamp black process, the channel black process and the gas black process. The different types of carbon blacks consist of elemental carbon in the form of aggregates. Over 95 % of worldwide CB production is produced using the oil furnace process, where heavy aromatic petroleum oils are pyrolysed at extremely high temperatures (1200-1800 °C) (Sahebdehfar & Soltanieh, 2023).

There are several challenges associated with the traditional production of CB:

- **Environmental impact:** The most significant challenge in conventional CB production is its devastating environmental impact. It has been reported that the emission of hazardous gases during production could hinder market growth. This is mainly due to the harmful release of various gases such as nitrogen oxide, carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, sulphur dioxide and particulate matter. These emissions not only have an environmental impact but also affect human health. Around 15 million metric tonnes of carbon black produced annually will emit 29-79 million metric tonnes of CO₂ each year (Rosner, Bhagde, Slaughter, Zorba, & Stokes-Draut, 2024). As a result, several stringent regulations have been imposed by governments. The process produces CB as a fine powder, which, if not well-contained, can become fugitive emissions, and contribute to air pollution.
- **Energy consumption:** The CB production process is very energy intensive. Reducing energy consumption and increasing process efficiency with minimum waste is a continuous challenge.

Hence, the carbon black industry cannot be seen as a sustainable long-term alternative and must be replaced by more sustainable options.

Technologies based on the decomposition of hydrocarbons for carbon production by plasma is a possible decarbonization option in the carbon black manufacturing process. These technologies also produce hydrogen.

Methane pyrolysis or methane cracking includes the dissociation of methane into low-carbon hydrogen and elemental carbon.

The main methane pyrolysis technologies can be grouped into three main divisions:

- Thermal: The most established technology and the process includes direct decomposition of methane using a heat source and the temperature will be greater than 1000 °C. This technology is considered a high-potential alternative to steam methane reforming (SMR).
- Catalytic: The temperature is reduced in the presence of a catalyst (around 800 °C) and provides better control of the properties of carbon. However, catalyst poisoning is a challenge.
- Plasma: This process uses either thermal or non-thermal energy sources to crack methane. This includes using microwave or electric arcs to deliver significant energy to methane.

This report focuses mainly on elemental carbon produced by non-thermal plasma dissociation of methane, being optimized in the ColdSpark® project. Figure 1 compares various methane pyrolysis methods with the ColdSpark® approach.

Figure 1. Comparison of different methane pyrolysis technologies (* T_e is the electron temperature)

Commercially available carbon black may contain impurities from the source materials. Due to the production method, varying amounts of adsorbed by-products, particularly aromatic compounds, may be present due to the large surface areas and surface characteristics. Classes of impurities identified are PAHs, nitro derivatives of PAHs and sulphur-containing PAHs (World Health Organisation, 1996).

The plasma reactor design influences the type of plasma produced and can affect the type and characteristics of the carbon produced. Power supply parameters such as rise pulse, waveform, pulse duration and repetition rate can enable reactor optimization. However, efficient carbon management such as preventing carbon build-up inside the reactor, ensuring continuous process flow, and carbon handling after separation, which includes large space requirements for storage, processing, loading and hauling away of carbon products, can be significant challenges during methane pyrolysis. Carbon management is nevertheless considered the biggest issue for methane pyrolysis as three tonnes of solid carbon is produced for each tonne of hydrogen. Carbon coking or carbon build-up, where carbon is deposited on the reactor electrode can reduce the heating efficiency, disrupt the plasma process and ultimately lead to a complete shutdown of the process.

Finding a suitable market for carbon utilization could also pose a major challenge. Proper collaborations between different industries are required to build a supply chain for carbon produced from methane pyrolysis as this would improve the overall economics of the process.

COLDSPARK® PRODUCTS

Hydrogen is an important feedstock for fertilizers, chemical synthesis, iron production, etc. and H₂ can decarbonize various industrial sectors. However, hydrogen in its free form is often required to be released from other molecules, such as H₂O or CH₄. According to the Global Hydrogen Review by the International Energy Agency (IEA), in 2022, the total global hydrogen production was 94 million tonnes (Mt H₂) with associated emissions of 900 Mt CO₂ and almost all were produced from fossil fuels (Agency I. E., 2022). Hence, it is crucial to focus on developing methods for producing hydrogen economically while minimizing CO₂ emissions. Substantial worldwide efforts have been developed to progress economic H₂ production technologies such as CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) facilities, water electrolysis using renewable electricity etc. However, none of the low-emission hydrogen production methods can compete with the current dominant industrial process, i.e., steam methane reforming, SMR,

According to Eq (1), every molecule of methane that undergoes steam methane reforming will produce one molecule of CO₂. Using the stoichiometry of reactions, CO₂ produced per hydrogen

mass equals 5.5 g CO₂/g H₂. This means that for every gram of hydrogen produced from SMR, 5.5 grams of CO₂ are emitted.

Estimating the exact amount of CO₂ emitted throughout the entire life cycle poses a significant challenge. CO₂ emissions from SMR vary depending on the process efficiency, natural gas purity, natural gas sources, transportation distance etc. Generally, SMR produces 7.5 to 12 tonnes of CO₂ / tonne of hydrogen produced (Katebah, Al-Rawashdeh, & Linke, 2022). This results in 720 million tonnes CO₂ eq. emissions per year (Gautier, Rohani, & Fulcheri, 2017).

CB market is projected to grow significantly to 24 million tonnes by 2035 (ChemAnalyst, 2023). 95 % of this CB is being produced with the furnace process. This process is characterised by direct CO₂ emissions with an average amount of 1.90 to 5.25 kg CO₂ per kg of CB (Rosner, Bhagde, Slaughter, Zorba, & Stokes-Draut, 2024), resulting in more than 50 million tonnes of CO₂ emissions annually and 0.125 % of the total worldwide emissions (Gautier, Rohani, & Fulcheri, 2017).

The plasma process aims to replace the two above-mentioned processes with an environmentally friendly process allowing the concurrent synthesis of low-carbon hydrogen and solid carbon (or CB) by directly cracking the methane.

Hence, because of several unique benefits, methane pyrolysis is by many experts (Weger, Abanades, & Butler, 2017), (Sanchez-Bastardo, Schlogl, & Ruland, 2021) seen as the most promising low-emission hydrogen production technology that splits CH₄ from natural gas or biogas into hydrogen and elemental carbon (Equation 2).

First, there is abundant natural gas (CH₄ as the main component). Further, sufficient renewable biogas (CH₄ as the main component) is also available from landfills, agricultural biomass, food waste, water treatment plants etc. If biogas is used for methane pyrolysis, then the process may even become carbon negative.

However, the mass ratio between H₂ and elemental carbon is 1:3 in methane pyrolysis. Thus, large quantities of elemental carbon will be produced during large-scale H₂ production during methane pyrolysis. The elemental carbon with the highest purity can be used as a raw material for carbon that is required in the industry. The carbon can also be valorised with collaboration from relevant industries to known carbon structures such as CB, graphite, carbon fibres, carbon nanotubes, etc, (presented in Figure 2), however, often with limited control over their characteristics and morphology. Also, there is a knowledge gap in understanding the carbon production mechanism by non-thermal plasma that can increase the uncertainty in controlling specifically the structures of carbon materials produced during the process.

Figure 2. Methane cracking by non-thermal plasma using high voltage power supply and powered by renewable energy

Several methane pyrolysis technology companies are currently engaged in extensive research to develop carbons with specific allotrope compositions. To ensure the successful commercialization of the carbon produced, it is necessary to further enhance its value. This requires significant investment in research and development to improve properties such as strength, flexibility, conductivity, durability etc. It also requires an advanced materials economy that fosters competitiveness in global markets, certification (e.g.- ASTM standards) etc.

During the transition from batch production to continuous feed in pyrolysis technologies, a notable challenge arises in the continuous removal of solid carbon without necessitating a process shutdown.

While production, removal and handling of elemental carbon can be an issue for profitable pyrolysis, the valorization of carbon can create additional value and improve the economics of the pyrolysis technology.

The most notable allotropes of carbon include CB, graphite, carbon nanotube and carbon fibres. The allotropes of carbon are mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1: Carbon allotropes

Carbon Allotrope	Illustration	Description
Carbon black		Usually spherical (Barrie, et al., 2004), with sizes ranging from a few nanometers to several micrometres. They are less regularly crystalline and are mostly amorphous.
Graphite	<p data-bbox="711 1648 911 1682">(Britannica, 2024)</p>	Has a layered structure consisting of rings of six carbon atoms arranged in horizontal sheets. Thus, the graphite crystallizes in the hexagonal system (Britannica, 2024)

<p>Graphene</p>	<p>(American Chemicals Society, 2024)</p>	<p>Considered as the building block for other carbon allotropes. They are two-dimensional forms of crystalline carbon, either a single layer of carbon atoms forming a hexagonal or honeycomb lattice or several coupled layers of this structure (Katsnelson, 2024).</p>
<p>Carbon nanotube</p>	<p>(Yirka, 2016)</p>	<p>Nanocarbon materials with tubular structures consisting of rolled graphene nanosheets (Ren, 2024).</p>
<p>Carbon fibres</p>	<p>(Huber, 2020)</p>	<p>Long chain, thin crystalline carbon filaments (Engineering, 2024)</p>
<p>Fullerene</p>	<p>(Porto, Silva, de Oliveira, Pereira, & Borges, 2019)</p>	<p>Hollow sphere created by a closed-end sheet and consists of hexagonal and pentagonal carbon rings (Walton & Kroto, 2024)</p>

Carbon can vary in size, measuring from mm to μm in size and is usually produced as a fine powder. Carbon samples from pyrolysis need to be tested to determine their specific properties, which will help identify specific applications. The applications of carbon black are related to its properties such as surface area, particle size, structure, electrical conductivity and colour (Sahebdehfar & Soltanieh, 2023).

This report includes discussions on carbon materials supplied by SEID AS, Norway, obtained from plasma pyrolysis of methane. Three batches of carbon samples were analyzed at the University of Stavanger (UiS) using various analytical techniques, including TEM, SEM, XRD, and Raman analysis, to evaluate the morphological characteristics and distinguish between graphitic and non-graphitic structures within the carbon material. Additionally, N_2 adsorption and iodine number analyses were conducted for surface area analysis.

The properties and grades of carbon black that determine its use are related to the surface area, particle size, and structure. A technical classification system developed by the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) grades the carbon blacks. It consists of a letter followed by a three-digit number (a four-character nomenclature system) (World Health Organisation, 1996). According to this system, N indicates the product gives a normal curing rate. The first digit indicates the typical average particle size, and the last two digits are assigned randomly (World Health Organisation, 1996). The analysis at the University of Stavanger confirmed that the CB produced in ColdSpark® is in the range of N220-N330 according to the study performed at the University of Stavanger and can be used in passenger car treads, commercial vehicle treads, industrial conveyor belts, anti-vibration-high amplitude mechanical rubber goods etc. The carbon samples from SEID will be optimized by changing the plasma reactor and power supply parameters. Hence, the results obtained cannot be considered final.

Marketing analysis

The green economy is setting trends for concurrent growth in both carbon use and hydrogen production capacity. Analyzing the market size and forecast for various carbon products provides crucial insights for stakeholders in these industries.

Along with the economic potential and trends, it is important to analyse the environmental and social impacts of the production and usage of carbon materials. The production of low CO_2 carbon feedstocks can contribute to sustainable development goals through innovative technologies such as non-thermal methane cracking for hydrogen production, which promises cleaner energy solutions.

In summary, this report highlights the critical role of carbon materials across various industries, showcasing their economic viability and potential for future market growth.

Table 2 Carbon products and their primary use*

Carbon products	Production Processes	Primary Uses	Market Size and Price
CB	Includes the furnace black process, thermal black process, and acetylene black process	Tires, printing inks, high-performance coatings and plastics (Dagle, et al., 2017)	Carbon Black demand will increase by roughly 70%, going from 14.5 MT in 2022 to 24 MT in 2035 (ChemAnalyst, 2023). The prices expected for the CB are in the range of \$0.4–2 /kg (Dagle, et al., 2017) depending on product requirements.
Graphite and Graphene	Graphite is mainly mined, and graphene is produced mechanically from graphite.	Graphite is used in various applications including lubricants and batteries; graphene is significant in the semiconductor and composites industries	Graphite had a market size of 250 K MT in 2020 (Dagle, et al., 2017) graphene had a size of 1.30 MT in 2022 (Statista, 2023). Graphite prices range from \$0.5 to \$2.7 per kilogram, while graphene is considerably more expensive at over \$10 per kilogram (Graphite, u.d.; Dagle, et al., 2017)
Carbon Fibres	Aerospace, automobiles, sports and leisure, construction, wind turbines, carbon-	Used in aerospace, automotive, sports, leisure, and construction industries.	The market was 160,000 tonnes in 2023, projected to rise to 415,000 tonnes by 2035. Prices range from \$20 to

	reinforced composite materials, and textiles (Dagle, et al., 2017)		\$113 per kilogram (ChemAnalyst, 2023).
Carbon Nanotubes	Produced by methods such as arc discharge, laser ablation, and chemical vapor deposition.	Used in composites to enhance thermal, electrical, and mechanical properties.	Market was about 2255,8 tonnes in 2018 and projected to be around 3931 tonnes in 2023. Prices vary widely from \$0.1 to \$600.00 per gram depending on the application (Moore, 2019).
Needle Coke	Produced by delayed coking of heavy residues after catalytic cracking in refineries.	Mainly used for graphite electrodes in electric arc steel furnaces.	The market size was 3.250 kt/a in 2021 (Analytica A. , 2023), with an expected increase to 6.7 million tonnes by 2031. The price is around \$2.5 per kilogram (Analytica A. , 2023).

*Data is provided by IREC market research related to the LCA of the ColdSpark® Technology

Carbon Black - dominantly used in tyres, printing inks, and high-performance coatings and plastics.

Market Growth and Trends: The market size was 14.5 million tonnes in 2022 and is projected to grow significantly to 24 million tonnes by 2035. This suggests a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of approximately 4.01% (ChemAnalyst, 2023). This growth is likely driven by expanding automotive industries, especially in developing economies, and the rising demand for high-performance materials in various sectors.

Price Dynamics: The price range of \$0.4 to \$2 per kilogram may fluctuate based on raw material costs and production efficiencies. Increasing regulations around emissions and environmental impacts might also influence production costs and pricing strategies.

Graphite and Graphene - graphite is used in lubricants, batteries, and other industrial applications. Graphene, with its exceptional properties, is crucial in the semiconductor and composites industries.

Market Growth and Trends: The graphite market was 250 000 tonnes in 2021, and the graphene market was 1.30 million tonnes in 2022. The growth in graphene, in particular, is expected to be substantial due to its increasing applications in high-tech industries. The drive towards more advanced electronic devices and renewable energy applications are major growth catalysts.

Price Dynamics: Graphite's price is relatively stable, ranging from \$0.5 to \$2.7 per kilogram. Graphene, being a more niche and technologically significant material, commands a much higher price, reflecting its unique properties and production complexities.

Carbon Fibres - extensively used in aerospace, automotive, sports, leisure, and construction due to their strength and lightweight properties.

Market Growth and Trends: Projected to rise from 160,000 tonnes in 2023 to 415,000 tonnes by 2035, indicating a CAGR of about 7,65 % (Chemanalyst, 2023). This growth is underpinned by the increasing demand for lightweight materials that reduce energy consumption and CO₂ emissions, particularly in the automotive and aerospace sectors.

Price Dynamics: The high price range (\$20 to \$113 per kilogram) reflects the complex manufacturing processes and the advanced applications of carbon fibres in industries where performance and weight reduction are critical.

Carbon Nanotubes - utilized to improve thermal, electrical, and mechanical properties in composite materials.

Market Growth and Trends: There was a significant market size decrease from approximately 2255,8 tonnes in 2018 to an estimated 3931 tonnes in 2023. This trend needs careful analysis as it may indicate production challenges, market saturation, or shifts towards alternative technologies.

Price Dynamics: The vast price ranges from \$0.1 to \$600.00 per gram indicates a highly application-specific market where value is driven by performance enhancements in high-end applications.

Needle Coke - primarily for graphite electrodes in electric arc steel furnaces.

Market Growth and Trends: The market is expected to grow from 3.25 million tonnes in 2021 to 6.7 million tonnes by 2031, reflecting increased demand from the steel industry, especially in electric arc furnace (EAF) operations, a cleaner alternative to traditional blast furnaces (Analytica A. , 2023).

Price Dynamics: The stable price of around \$2.5 per kilogram may adjust depending on crude oil prices and the demand-supply balance in the steel industry (Analytica A. , 2023).

Figure 3 shows the 2020 market size for carbon derivatives and Figure 4 shows the market prices and predicted market price in 2035.

Figure 3. 2020 and future market size for carbon derivatives

Figure 4. 2020 market prices of carbon derivatives (IGTPAN & Technology, 2016)

(The numbers are indicative based on the information in the table above as the carbon derivatives can vary depending on the application requirements, physical parameters and the amounts)

Current situation on the carbon and EU trends

The European Commission communication outlines carbon cycles (European Commission, 2021), which involves both natural and technological processes related to CO₂ emissions or carbon utilization as a raw material. These processes aim to manage and potentially reduce carbon emissions into the atmosphere through three distinct methods:

- Utilization: Increasing the recycling or reuse of carbon feedstock in products and processes.
- Removal: Sequestration of CO₂ via natural processes.
- Storage: Direct air capture of carbon or storage of carbon products.

Each of these processes offers diverse approaches, currently at various stages of implementation, with some requiring further development in terms of market or technology readiness.

Integrating a focus on substituting and recycling carbon into products and processes aligns industrial policy with climate policy, promoting circularity in resource flows. This integration can deliver climate and environmental benefits. A [2021 EPRS briefing](#) highlights a range of nature-based or technological Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) solutions (Erbach & Victoria, 2021). These solutions range from nature-based practices like forestation, soil carbon sequestration, and wetland restoration, to technological alternatives such as enhanced weathering, bioenergy with carbon capture and storage, and direct air capture and storage. Nature-based solutions are currently more cost-effective and viable in the short term, while some technological alternatives have the potential to become more significant later this century. While the Commission's communication broadly encompasses various options for CDR, it specifically targets also actions to promote new business models incentivizing carbon farming practices and scaling up sustainable carbon capture, recycling, transport, and storage by fostering new industrial value chains.

The carbon economy encompasses all sectors and systems reliant on carbon-containing resources, including organic carbon in animals, plants, microorganisms, and derived biomass; organic waste; fossil resources such as coal, oil, and gas; and inorganic carbon in various compounds like basalt rocks or other carbon mineralisation processes (European Commission, 2021). This interlinked system includes land and marine ecosystems producing bio-based carbon, deposits of fossil resources, primary production sectors utilizing and producing carbon resources, and economic and industrial sectors utilizing carbon-containing resources and processes.

Sustainable carbon resource management evaluates whether a sector's resource demand can be decarbonized or remains persistently reliant on carbon inputs. It explores methods to make carbon demand independent of fossil resources, utilizing renewable carbon sources that avoid or substitute additional fossil carbon from the geosphere. Thus, renewable carbon does not

contribute to increasing the CO₂ content in the atmosphere and contributes to mitigating climate change.

CB, renowned for its versatility, finds diverse applications across various industries owing to its exceptional properties. Here are some key sectors where CB serves as a fundamental raw material:

Rubber Industry: In the manufacturing of tyres, CB plays a pivotal role by reinforcing rubber compounds, thereby enhancing tyre strength, durability, and resistance to wear.

Plastics Industry: In masterbatch production, CB serves as both a colouring agent and a reinforcement additive, contributing to the strength and UV resistance of plastic products.

Ink and Toner Manufacturing: CB serves as a prevalent pigment in printing inks, imparting black colouration and contributing to ink viscosity and stability. Additionally, it is utilized in toner formulations for laser printers and photocopiers.

Paints and Coatings: In the automotive sector, CB acts as a pigment and UV stabilizer in automotive coatings, and industrial coatings, including those used for metal protection.

Textile Industry: In textile fibre production, CB is occasionally added to synthetic fibres during manufacturing to enhance colour and improve fibre properties.

Electronics: CB serves as a conductive additive in battery manufacturing, enhancing electrical conductivity and overall battery performance.

Construction Materials: In the construction industry, CB is utilized in the formulation of sealants and adhesives, offering reinforcement and UV resistance.

Adhesives and Sealants: CB is incorporated into rubber-based adhesives to enhance strength and durability.

Automotive Industry: CB is used in the production of various automotive components, such as belts, hoses, gaskets, and seals, to improve mechanical properties.

Cables and Wires: In cable insulation materials, CB provides electrical conductivity and UV resistance.

Consumer Products: In footwear manufacturing, CB is utilized in the production of black-coloured rubber soles for shoes.

Agriculture: CB is added to agricultural mulch films to augment durability and resistance to UV radiation (Hernandez-Charpak, Mozrall, Williams, & Trabold, 2024).

Wastewater treatment : carbon nanotubes, activated carbon, graphene and its derivatives, and fullerene have found potent applications in wastewater treatment (Kumari, Kaur, & Dhania, 2023)

Soil modifiers: Nanoclay can be used for soil stabilization in various industries and applications (Sedighi & Farhadian, 2023).

Support materials for metal catalysts: allow the dispersion and stabilization of small metal particles on a surface. Compared to the bulk metal, these catalyst preparations present a higher surface area of catalytically active atoms. The use of activated carbon as support for metal catalysts shows several advantages compared to other support materials (Iwanow, Gartner, Sieber, & Konig, 2020).

These examples underscore the expansive utility of CB, which continues to evolve with the emergence of new applications and technologies. Its versatility, coupled with its reinforcing and colouring properties, renders it a valuable raw material across a myriad of industries.

Industry analysis

The hydrogen and carbon produced with the ColdSpark® technology offer great opportunities. Avoiding direct CO₂ emissions implies reduced GHG emissions compared to the traditional H₂ production processes such as SMR and coal gasification. In methane pyrolysis, the solid carbon produced can be safely stored without emissions for an indefinite period. The resulting carbon holds significant value as an essential industrial raw material, finding applications in industries such as aluminium, steel, and construction. Additionally, it serves as a viable substitute for graphite in battery materials, offering diverse opportunities for utilization. For instance, its incorporation into bipolar plates for stacks has already demonstrated enhanced efficiency, potentially stimulating local job creation in Europe and reducing import dependency diversification. Notably, its potential applications in the agricultural sector, particularly for soil enhancement, show promise.

Graphite finds application in steelmaking, battery production, and industries such as semiconductor and solar. Through subsequent industrial processes, amorphous carbon can be transformed into graphene. Graphite possesses exceptional strength and conductivity, and its utilization is progressively expanding across sectors such as aerospace, automotive, wind power, and construction.

The challenge for the Global economy is that we require coal in several industries to produce essential products for the world, e.g., steel, silicon, etc. Approximately 30 % of this coal is required for various industrial purposes, including steel, cement, aluminium, chemicals, fertiliser and synthetic rubber production (Agency I. R., 2022). These industries rely heavily on the elemental carbon content to produce their products.

The objective is to identify a solution that will reduce our dependence on coal to mitigate climate change. In a world, where we need to move away from fossil fuels including coal, a path should be identified to replace the aforementioned 30 % solid carbon. If the carbon produced by cold methane pyrolysis without emitting greenhouse gases, can be used as a valuable resource in commercial applications, this would reduce the coal dependency in the future. The carbon produced from ColdSpark® using a non-thermal plasma technology has potential environmental advantages when powered by renewable energy with low carbon emissions, if compared to the thermal black process.

Furthermore, the hydrogen produced during cold methane pyrolysis can be utilised as a viable resource. However, methane pyrolysis using non-thermal plasma is still in its early stages but has the potential to be scaled up rapidly to meet the growing demand for elemental carbon.

The current results from the analysis of the carbon samples produced during the lab-scale ColdSpark® methane cracking process show a very high-purity carbon. In light of the current market dynamics, there are two primary pathways for carbon utilization currently being explored:

- **Industry Applications:** The first results obtained from the ColdSpark® project hold promise for applications in the metal and tyre industries, serving as a sustainable alternative to conventional carbon sources. These industries require carbon in substantial volumes. The process aims to cater to these sectors, providing a significant market for bulk carbon.
- **High-Quality Applications:** These applications are of great importance in sectors such as batteries and other applications that require high-quality carbon with high purity. However, the market size for such applications may not be as substantial as that of bulk industries.

Preliminary analysis of carbon produced in SEID's reactor showed N220 and N330 CB grades. N220 and N330 are two common grades of carbon used in various industries. N220 CB is characterized by its smaller particle size and is commonly used as a reinforcing filler in rubber compounds and improves mechanical properties such as tensile strength, tear resistance and abrasion resistance

Steel industry

Steel manufacturing is one of the most energy-intensive industries in the world. Current steel production in the world is more than 1.7 billion tonnes of steel/per year and most of this steel production requires coking coal and 770 kg of metallurgical coal to produce one tonne of steel (Sahajwalla, Maroufi, Bell, Bell, & De Bari, 2019). This results in significant emissions of CO₂ to the atmosphere and alternative sources of coking coal could help mitigate the industry's reliance on coal. According to (Sahajwalla, Maroufi, Bell, Bell, & De Bari, 2019), approximately 1.1 billion tonnes of coking coal is consumed annually. With an increasing demand for steel, more and more coal will be used and hence, there is a risk of depletion of suitable coal reserves, which could lead to

shortages and high prices if the supply declines faster than demand. Also, due to rising costs, and stringent environmental regulations related to CO₂ generation, steelmaking industries are seeking new ways to reduce their coal dependency (De Clercq, Doyle, & Voet, 2022) and replace with alternative carbon sources with lower CO₂ emissions without affecting the process efficiency (Sahajwalla, Maroufi, Bell, Bell, & De Bari, 2019).

The carbon produced by ColdSpark® is of very high purity as no catalyst is used in the methane pyrolysis process using non-thermal plasma. This could reduce several treatment steps to purify carbon from catalysts.

Tyre industry

Based on particle size and N₂ surface area analysis, the carbon produced falls within the category of N220-N330 CB's and the lattice characteristics resemble furnace black. N220 is often utilized in the manufacturing of tyre treads that require high durability and strength.

N330 is also used as a reinforcing filler in rubber compounds, offering good reinforcement properties along with improved processibility. N330 finds applications in tyre sidewalls, inner liners, moulded rubber products, automotive components and various industrial rubber goods where a balance between reinforcement and processibility is desired.

Silicon production

Silicon is produced by the reduction of silicon dioxide with carbonaceous reducing agents such as petroleum coke, coal and charcoal at high temperatures (> 2000 °C) using the Acheson Process (W.R.Matizamhuka, 2019) . This results in large CO₂ emissions around 5 kg of CO₂ per kilogram of silicon produced (without emissions related to electric power generations) (Philipson, et al., 2022). Thus, the silicon industry like the steel industry, is an energy-intensive industry from both an economic and environmental perspective. Thus, replacing coal obtained from mines or derived from petroleum with carbon produced from natural gas or biomethane using non-thermal plasma technology could reduce CO₂ emissions to a great extent.

Other application areas

Some other diverse applications of ColdSpark®'s carbon, however, extend beyond traditional sectors adding several diverse applications and additional areas of interest, which should be further investigated:

- Carbon Concrete or carbon rebar: Ongoing research explores the incorporation of carbon into cement mixtures, aiming to reduce CO₂ emissions in concrete production, a significant contributor to carbon footprints in the construction sector. Key characteristics and advantages of carbon rebar include high strength often surpassing the strength of traditional

steel rebar while being much lighter in weight. Corrosion resistance, unlike steel, carbon rebar does not corrode resulting in low maintenance, making it ideal for applications in aggressive environments, such as marine structures, chemical plants, or regions with high humidity (Zhu, et al., 2023).

- **Quantum Dots:** The fine, small-sized carbon produced may find numerous applications in several disciplines including biomedicine, catalysis, optoelectronic devices, and anticounterfeiting, presenting opportunities for application of the carbon received in advanced technologies. For example, carbon dots (CDs) are luminescent nanoparticles classified as graphene quantum dots composed of one to several graphene layers often functionalised with molecular groups at the edges (Stepanidenko, Ushakova, Fedorov, & Rogach, 2021).

Competition analysis

In evaluating the competitive landscape for the production of carbon as a feedstock, it's crucial to consider several factors including key players, production methodologies, geographic market segmentation, and the evolving application sectors. Carbon feedstock, especially in forms like CB, graphite, graphene, carbon fibres, and carbon nanotubes, serves a broad range of industrial applications. Here's a comprehensive analysis of these factors:

I. Key Players in the Market

Monolith Inc.: Monolith is the most advanced methane pyrolysis technology company which is operating at 14,000 tonnes/year of carbon black at Olive Creek 1, Nebraska and selling CB to Goodyear for tyre manufacturing (Greenwood, 2022). This process uses high-temperature electric heating plasma.

Cabot Corporation: A leading US producer of CB, involved in enhancing material properties for rubber and plastic applications, particularly in the automotive sector.

Carbon Black Manufacturer & Suppliers | Birla Carbon: Birla Carbon is one of the world's largest manufacturers of carbon black and has CB applications in mechanical rubber goods, plastics, coatings, adhesives etc.

Orion Engineered Carbons S.A.: Another significant player (Luxemburg) in the CB market, known for a wide range of CB products that serve various sectors including automotive, industrial, and coatings.

GrafTech International: A major producer of graphite electrodes (USA), an essential component of steel production via electric arc furnaces.

Hexcel Corporation: Known for manufacturing advanced composite materials including carbon fibres, targeting aerospace and defence applications (USA).

Hyperion Materials & Technologies: (HQ Finland) Specializes in advanced hard and super-hard materials, including synthetic diamond and cubic boron nitride, with potential overlap in the carbon feedstock domain through technological innovation.

II. Production methodologies

Carbon Black: Produced primarily through the furnace black process, thermal black process, and acetylene black process, each with distinct characteristics suited to different product specifications and uses.

Graphite and Graphene: Extracted from natural sources or synthesized using high-cost, high-purity methods that are crucial for electronics and composite materials.

Carbon Fibres and Nanotubes: Made from various precursors like polyacrylonitrile (PAN) and pitch, requiring specialized processes such as controlled heating and stretching to achieve desired material properties.

III. Geographic Market Segmentation

Asia-Pacific: Dominates the production and consumption of carbon materials, largely due to the extensive manufacturing base in China, which is a major player in graphite mining and also leads in the production of carbon fibres and nanotubes.

North America and Europe: These regions focus on advanced material technologies and have high consumption rates of carbon products in aerospace, automotive, and electronics applications.

Emerging Markets: Countries like India and Brazil are rapidly expanding their manufacturing capabilities and could represent significant growth areas for carbon feedstock usage, especially in automotive and industrial applications.

IV. Evolving Application Sectors

Renewable Energy: Carbon materials, especially graphene and carbon fibres, are increasingly used in solar panels, wind turbines, and batteries, driving growth in the renewable energy sector.

Electronics: With the miniaturization and sophistication of electronic devices, high-purity graphite and graphene are in high demand for their superior electrical properties.

Automotive: As the automotive industry shifts towards electric vehicles, the demand for carbon materials in batteries, tyres, and lightweight structural components is expected to rise.

Aerospace: Carbon fibres are critical for producing lightweight, high-strength materials for aircraft and spacecraft, an area with significant growth potential given the global expansion in aerospace capabilities.

V. Competitive Strategy Recommendations

To navigate the competitive landscape of carbon production as a feedstock effectively, companies should consider the following strategic actions:

- Innovation in production techniques: Developing cost-effective and environmentally friendly production methods to reduce overhead and attract clients prioritizing sustainability.
- Market expansion: Entering emerging markets with growing industrial bases can provide new revenue streams and reduce dependency on saturated markets.
- Collaborations and partnerships: Working with other industry leaders can help in sharing technological insights and accessing new markets, particularly in high-technology sectors like electronics and renewable energy.
- Focus on speciality products: Companies could focus on producing high-value, specialized carbon products like high-purity graphene and multi-walled carbon nanotubes, which have less competition and higher profit margins.

This competition analysis can help further understand the intricacies of the carbon production market, and plan and strategically position ColdSpark®'s carbon-related investigations and operations for sustained growth.

Perspective analysis

In order to evaluate and understand the various factors that influence strategic planning, and the potential and future possibilities of the market, a comprehensive approach is used in the following section. It combines multiple analytical frameworks to provide a holistic view of the internal and external environments. SWOT analysis, PEST analysis, and Environmental Analysis are used to support the identification of the major internal attributes and resources that support and may work against successful results. Then external factors which can be capitalized on or use as advantage for future production as well as such factors that could cause trouble for the market realization are also examined. The impact of government policies, regulations, economic trends, societal trends, cultural norms, and consumer behaviours combined with technological advancements, innovations, and Intellectual Privacy Rights (IPR) are also touched upon.

The integration of these analyses provides a more nuanced understanding of the possible strategic position, can help identification of potential risks and opportunities, and develop more effective strategies to approach for realization of the carbon produced by ColdSpark®.

SWOT

The SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis (Figure 5) provides a framework to evaluate the strategic positioning and potential of ColdSpark®'s carbon production using non-thermal plasma technology. This analysis considers internal factors (strengths and weaknesses) and external factors (opportunities and threats) relevant to the initiative.

Figure 5: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats analysis for ColdSpark® carbon market potential

PEST (political, economic, social and technological) analysis for the deployment of a CB substrate produced via cold pyrolysis of methane as shown in Figure 6:

Figure 6. PEST analysis

The environmental benefits of using ColdSpark®'s sustainable carbon production process compared to traditional coal-based carbon production are substantial. ColdSpark®'s approach aligns well with key European environmental initiatives such as the European Green Deal and the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS). Below, we detail these benefits and contextualize them within these frameworks (Figure 7):

<p>Reduction</p>	<p>ColdSpark®'s process produces carbon as additional product of hydrogen generation without emitting CO₂, directly reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Traditional coal-based carbon production utilizes coal combustion for carbon production is a significant source of CO₂ emissions. Switching from coal to ColdSpark®'s method directly supports carbon reduction targets.</p>
<p>Improvement</p>	<p>Support reduction of coal mining environmental impacts and utilization of natural gas or biomethane. ColdSpark®'s process does not rely on coal or other fossil fuels, thereby eliminating the environmental degradation associated with mining activities such as landscape disruption, habitat destruction, and soil contamination. Traditional coal mining has extensive environmental impacts, including deforestation, soil erosion, water contamination, and biodiversity loss. Instead, ColdSpark® utilizes natural gas or biomethane as a feed stock, further bolstering its eco-friendly credentials.</p>
<p>Reduce</p>	<p>ColdSpark®'s process when the carbon production facilities are located near or at the site of hydrogen usage (or vice versa), transportation requirements and associated emissions can be significantly reduced. In traditional methods coal transport, whether by truck, rail, or ship, not only consumes significant energy but also contributes to traffic congestion and air pollution.</p>

Figure 7. Environmental benefits from CB production using cold methane pyrolysis technology

Alignment with the European Green Deal

The European Green Deal aims to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050, promoting a green transition in various sectors. ColdSpark®'s technology supports this vision by:

- By producing hydrogen and carbon without direct CO₂ emissions, ColdSpark®'s process aligns with the EU's goal and EU Climate Law (24 June 2021), which legally binds a target of reducing emissions by 55% by 2030 and climate neutrality by 2050. The hydrogen produced with the ColdSpark® technology can be classified as low carbon according to the new [rules of the EU for H2](#). This also affects the impact related to emissions of the produced carbon.
- Carbon production from biomethane supports the EU's focus on reducing waste and improving resource efficiency, which aligns with the principles of Circular Economy.

Compliance with the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS)

The EU ETS sets caps on the total amount of certain greenhouse gases that installations covered by a system can emit. It operates on the "cap and trade" principle, where companies receive or buy emission allowances which they can trade as needed. Currently, it covers the large, energy-intensive industries, fossil-based electricity generation and aviation and is a main tool of the EU Green Deal for reaching climate neutrality by 2050. It is planned that in 2027 smaller industries, road transport and heating buildings will have a separate and new ETS. As the essence of the ETS is trading with the carbon emissions by not producing CO₂, ColdSpark®'s method could significantly reduce the amount of allowances that an operation needs to procure and hold, thereby lowering operational costs and enhancing the competitiveness of the technology. On the other hand, companies using ColdSpark®'s technology could potentially earn carbon credits for reducing emissions, which they could then sell on the EU ETS market, providing an additional revenue stream.

The transition from traditional coal-based carbon production to ColdSpark®'s innovative method offers profound environmental advantages, directly supporting the goals of the European Green Deal and adhering to the regulations of the EU ETS. By adopting ColdSpark®'s technology, industries not only mitigate their environmental impact but also align with broader EU policies aimed at achieving a sustainable, low-carbon economy. This strategic alignment not only fosters regulatory compliance but also positions companies well within emerging green markets.

E-carbon®

The awarding of a trademark for "eCarbon®" to SEID AS by the Norwegian Industrial Property Office marks a significant milestone in the realm of sustainable materials production. eCarbon®, produced via the innovative ColdSpark® process, represents a groundbreaking advancement in the

field of elemental carbon manufacturing. The carbon produced by ColdSpark® is already registered under the trademark eCarbon®. It can be an eco-friendly alternative for industries currently reliant on coal. It mitigates fugitive methane emissions (Kholod, et al., 2020) and contributes to a lower CO₂ footprint.

The ColdSpark® process, developed by the project, stands out as a pioneering method for producing elemental carbon. Unlike traditional carbon production processes, ColdSpark® is characterized by its cleanliness and efficiency. It minimizes environmental impact by utilizing sustainable practices and reducing carbon emissions. This aligns perfectly with the growing global need for eco-friendly alternatives and the urgent call for reducing carbon footprints.

eCarbon®, as a product of the ColdSpark® process, holds immense promise for various industries and applications. Its high-performance characteristics make it suitable for a wide range of uses, from advanced materials in construction to innovative components in electronics. Moreover, its sustainable production method ensures that it meets the increasing demand for environmentally conscious solutions.

The recognition of "eCarbon®" as a trademark underscores the project's dedication to innovation and sustainability. It signifies the technological achievement and the commitment to developing materials that contribute to a greener future. In a world where the importance of sustainable practices is ever-growing, the emergence of eCarbon® represents a significant step towards meeting the need for green carbon alternatives.

The plan for producing elemental carbon from biogas during the later stage of the project is represented in Figure 8. Currently, methane is used to produce hydrogen and solid carbon.

Figure 8: The planned carbon and hydrogen production process from biogas in ColdSpark®

Possible ways to mitigate challenges on the way to the market

As mentioned above, many challenges could affect the carbon market's potential. However, their effect could be mitigated to some extent by the following actions:

- By providing adequate funding opportunities and encouraging industry partnerships, it is possible to advance and expand methane pyrolysis technology development and accelerate the way to commercialization.
- Establish a pathway to bring together academia, technology developers, regulatory authorities, financial investors and industries to work on developing a strong carbon market.
- Promote methane pyrolysis as a low-carbon hydrogen production technology and continue to increase the market demand for carbon and hydrogen.
- Create a database of carbon types and their properties and evaluate the applications and markets for produced carbon by investigating market sizes and potential applications.

Conclusion

ColdSpark® has been successfully exploring carbon exploitation pathways by combining innovation, economic viability, and environmental responsibility. The project is committed to optimize the hydrogen production process and ensuring the valuable carbon produced is valorised successfully. This positions it as a significant and promising solution in the development of diverse methods for sustainable energy production.

The carbon product markets are diverse, with each product catering to specific industrial needs. The future growth in these markets will likely be influenced by technological advancements, regulatory policies, and shifts in global economic and industrial activities. Continued investment in research and development, particularly for high-performance applications like graphene and carbon fibres, is essential for maintaining market growth and sustainability.

As the ColdSpark® project progresses in its efforts to optimize the process for large-scale industrial application, various challenges are likely to emerge at each stage. While the current focus is on producing elemental carbon, the optimization process could result in variations in carbon quality. Therefore, it is important to ensure that the process remains scalable, as this could have a significant impact on the final characteristics of the carbon produced.

Replacing the current coal market with elemental carbon from methane pyrolysis will have several potential benefits, including reduced carbon emissions. Methane pyrolysis has the potential to produce elemental carbon with significantly lower carbon emissions compared to coal. This process generates carbon while releasing hydrogen as another product, which can be stored or

used as a clean fuel. This has the potential to contribute to reduced carbon emissions, counteract climate change, help countries meet emission reduction targets, and support sustainability goals.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

- o Deliverable 7.8 has been developed in accordance with the provision outlined within the following related documents:

ID	Reference or Related Document	Source or Link/Location
1	ColdSpark® Grant Agreement	ColdSpark® MS Teams
2	ColdSpark® Consortium Agreement Nr. 101069931	ColdSpark® MS Teams
3	D7.1. Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (M6)	ColdSpark® MS Teams
4	D7.2. Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (M12)	ColdSpark® MS Teams
5	D 1.7. Report on investigation of carbon quality and the application of produced carbon	ColdSpark® MS Teams

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